
Research

Research on the Impact of Digital Transformation on Production and Operation Management of Mongolian Mining Enterprises

Delgertsogt Ganchimeg^{1*}, Xi Xiuyan¹

¹Department of International Cooperation and Exchange, Dalian Jiaotong University, 794 Huanghe Road, Shahekou, Dalian, China

Abstract: This study delves into the impact of digital transformation on production and operations management within Mongolian mining enterprises, aiming to assess how this transformation affects various key dimensions including technology, information, cognition, organization, and management. Through the design and implementation of surveys, the study gathered perceptions and evaluations of digital transformation practices from employees of Mongolian mining companies. Subsequent reliability and validity tests ensured the credibility and efficacy of the data. The findings reveal that the majority of respondents agree digital transformation has effectively fostered internal unity and collaboration, addressing issues of management dispersion and information silos, thus enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of production and operations management. In terms of technology, digital transformation has raised the requirements for enterprise infrastructure and hardware, and spurred the development and use of new digital production and operations management software. From an informational perspective, it has provided businesses with a wealth of data resources, increasing the accuracy and timeliness of information, albeit also raising the workload for managers in data analysis. Cognitively, the mining industry has a clear understanding of the policy support and industry development requirements for digital transformation, yet gaps in overall planning and talent development remain. Organizationally, digital transformation has prompted a shift in the roles of production and operations management personnel, heightened professional requirements, and altered the role of management departments in analysis and decision-making. The management dimension highlights the positive role of digital transformation in supporting the analysis and control of production and operations management systems, enhancing management levels, and decision-making efficiency.

In conclusion, digital transformation has significantly impacted the production and operations management of Mongolian mining enterprises, not only optimizing management processes and improving operational efficiency but also enhancing competitive edge through technological innovation and effective utilization of information resources. However, challenges such as talent development, system integration, and data management persist and require attention and resolution in future transformation efforts. This study provides empirical analysis and insights into the digital transformation of Mongolian mining enterprises, offering a reference for formulating digital strategies and implementation plans. It also holds relevance for the digital transformation practices of mining enterprises in other countries and regions.

Keywords: Mongolia; Mining Enterprises; Digital Transformation; Production and Operations Management

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 21 April, 2024; **Published:** 23 April, 2024

How to cite this article: Delgertsogt Ganchimeg, Xi Xiuyan (2024). *Research on the Impact of Digital Transformation on Production and Operation Management of Mongolian Mining Enterprises*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(4), 92-100. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11048334>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2022 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Research background Mongolia's mining sector is the core of its economy. It is rich in coal, copper, iron and other mineral resources and has huge development prospects. With the rise of digital transformation around the world, the industry has gradually realized the importance of adopting advanced digital technologies and information systems to achieve business automation and digital management. The application of digital transformation in mining is not only a strategy to enhance corporate competitiveness, but also a means to optimize production and operation management through technological innovation. Driven by digital transformation, Mongolian mining companies have begun to explore the integration of information technology into production processes to improve efficiency and production accuracy. Specifically, the application of digital technology allows for real-time monitoring and data analysis of production activities, allowing timely identification and resolution of problems and anomalies in production. In addition, digital transformation helps improve production efficiency and reduce operating costs by optimizing supply chain management and realizing digital collaboration in the supply chain. Through continuous digital monitoring and analysis, mining companies can enhance the stability and reliability of product quality, thereby improving customer satisfaction, and reduce pollution and promote sustainable development through digital management of environmental risks. Taking a mining company in Mongolia as a case, this study aims to explore how digital transformation can revolutionize its production and operation management processes, thereby improving the company's market competitiveness and production efficiency. During the company's digital transformation process, it achieved comprehensive digital management of production and operation processes by introducing cutting-edge information technologies such as the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence. This not only enables enterprises to track key production indicators in real time and adjust and optimize production activities in a timely manner, but also further enhances the market competitiveness of enterprises by improving supply chain efficiency and reducing costs. In addition, the application of digital control methods effectively reduces environmental risks and pollution, providing a solid foundation for the sustainable development of enterprises.

Research Background

The purpose of this topic is to explore the impact of digital transformation on the production and operation management of Mongolian mining enterprises, and to study how digital transformation changes the production and operation management processes and improves the competitiveness and production efficiency of enterprises. Under the influence of the global digitalization wave, digital transformation has become an important way for companies to improve their competitiveness and production efficiency, especially for Mongolian mining companies. By studying the impact of digital transformation, we can better understand the advantages and applications of digital transformation, and provide reference for Mongolian mining companies to achieve digital transformation. At the same time, it will also help promote the sustainable development of Mongolia's mining industry and improve resource utilization efficiency and environmental protection levels.

Significance: Research significance Digital transformation has become an important way for global companies to improve production efficiency and competitiveness, and for mining companies, digital transformation is particularly important. Taking Mongolian mining companies as an example, studying the impact of digital transformation on production and operation management is of great theoretical and practical significance.

Theoretical significance Enriching the research field of digital transformation: Digital transformation has become an important way for global enterprises to improve production efficiency and competitiveness. However, there are

relatively few studies on digital transformation in the mining field. Therefore, by studying the impact of digital transformation on the production and operation management of Mongolian mining enterprises, we can provide new ideas and perspectives for the research on digital transformation in the mining field. Explore the impact of digital transformation on sustainable development: The production activities of mining companies have a very large impact on the environment and society, so digital transformation is of great significance to the sustainable development of mining companies. By studying the impact of digital transformation on Mongolian mining companies, we can explore the impact of digital transformation on the sustainable development of mining companies and provide new ideas for sustainable development in the mining field. Enhance the application of digital transformation in the field of production and operation management: The application of digital transformation in the field of production and operation management has achieved certain results, but there is still a lot of room for development. By studying the impact of digital transformation on the production and operation management of Mongolian mining enterprises, we can provide new ideas and methods for the application of digital transformation in the field of production and operation management. (2) Practical significance Improve the production efficiency and competitiveness of Mongolian mining enterprises: Digital transformation can realize digital management of the mine production process and improve the efficiency and accuracy of mine production through the application of advanced information technology. Through digital technology, the production process can be monitored and data analyzed in real time, problems and abnormalities can be discovered in a timely manner, and the flexibility and response speed of production operation management can be improved. Digital transformation can also improve supply chain management, realize digital collaboration of the supply chain, improve production efficiency and reduce costs, thereby improving the production efficiency and competitiveness of Mongolian mining companies.

Current status of digital operation and management of mining enterprises in Mongolia Geological condition:

Mongolia is located in central Asia, bordering Russia to the north and China to the east, south, and west, sharing a 4,670-kilometer national border. The country is rich in mineral resources underground. More than 80 types of mineral resources have been discovered, covering more than 6,000 deposits, and the total reserves are estimated to exceed 50 billion tons. Among them, about 500 mineral deposits involving more than 10 minerals have been evaluated in detail, and about 150 mineral deposits are being mined, but most mineral resources are still under development. In contrast, although China is a country rich in resources, its per capita resource possessions are only half of the world average. In particular, the proven reserves of the 16 mineral resources that play an important role in the national economy are seriously insufficient. Against this background, investing in Mongolia's mining development is not only an effective way to solve China's shortage of mineral resources, but also has important strategic significance for ensuring the stable operation of the national economy. By strengthening mining cooperation with Mongolia, it can provide China with a more stable supply of resources, thereby helping to alleviate domestic resource pressure and promote the common development of both economies.

Production and resources situation

Mongolia, located in the center of Asia, is famous for its vast territory, sparse population and rich natural resources. The country is particularly rich in underground resources. After preliminary exploration, it has been confirmed that they include coal, copper, gold, silver, iron, molybdenum, tungsten, tin, lead, zinc, platinum, uranium, silicon, phosphorus, donite, petroleum and gypsum. Including more than 80 mineral resources, more than 6,000 mineral deposits, and total reserves of more than 50 billion tons. Among these resources, proven reserves of coal, copper, phosphorus, fluorite and celestite occupy a prominent position globally, while the reserves and quality of diamond deposits and associated minerals are comparable to those in South Africa. Mongolia’s mineral resources rank second only to China, Russia and the United States in the global rankings. This prediction was made by Mongolian geologists, highlighting the country’s important position in the global mineral resources map.

In 2021, Mongolia's mineral mining and export activities have been significantly affected by the COVID-19 epidemic. In particular, the closure of China's borders due to the epidemic has had a major impact on its main mineral exports. Coal mining volume reached 21.3029 million tons, but its export volume dropped to 15.9417 million tons, a decrease of 44.3% from the same period in 2020. In addition, copper concentrate exports were 1.2386 million tons, down 11% from the previous year, while iron concentrate exports fell by 15% to 6.8916 million tons. Nevertheless, thanks to the continued high price of copper concentrate on the world market, Mongolia's copper concentrate export completion rate exceeded the planned 111%. In the financial sector, the Central Bank of Mongolia purchased 20.60 tons of gold during this period. Although it was 12.5% lower than the same period in 2020, it still reached 103% of the plan approved by the national budget. In terms of oil, Mongolia mined 4.6665 million barrels of oil in 2021 and exported 4.0904 million barrels. As of December 30, 2021, Mongolia’s total national fuel reserves are 117,262 tons, including 10,808 t tons of A-80 gasoline, 40,579 tons of AI-92 gasoline, and 58,761 tons of diesel. AI-92/ The reserves of No. 95 and No. 98 gasoline can last for 27 days, with a total reserve of 60,063 tons

Table 3.2 Foreign Investment in Mongolia (Unit: Billion USD)

Years	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Flow	-42	25	22	24	17
Stock (as of the end of 2022)	242	226	242	268	273

Figure4.3 Coal Production at Tavan Tolgoi from 2016 to 2022 (Unit: Million Tons)

Evaluation of digital production operations of Mongolian mining enterprises based on analytic hierarchy process

1. Evaluation method

(1) Analytic hierarchy process

Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a structured decision-making method proposed by Thomas L. Saaty in the 1970s. This approach allows decision makers to set priorities among a range of criteria and options to solve complex decision-making problems. The following are the basic components and steps of the AHP method:

① Establishment of hierarchical structure model of the problem:

AHP decomposes decision-making problems into different levels such as goals, criteria and solutions:

Goal level: Clearly state the problem or goal that requires decision-making.

Criterion level: Sets a set of criteria that determine whether an option is good or bad.

Solution layer: Possible solutions or options.

② Establish a judgment matrix:

By comparing the elements of each layer pairwise, a judgment matrix is formed. A scale of 1-9 is often used to describe the relative importance of elements. For example, if two elements A and B are equally important, then $A/B=1$; if A is extremely important, compared to B, $A/B=9$ can be set.

In this step, the Nine-Level Scale Method is generally used for scoring rules to construct a judgment matrix. The "Nine-Level Scale Method" is usually used in the scoring process in Multi-Attribute Decision Analysis (MADM). This method is mainly based on the orderly quantitative evaluation of various attributes or indicators of different evaluation objects or solutions. The core of the nine-level scaling method is to use a grade scale from 1 to 9 to express the relative importance or superiority of different evaluation objects on a certain indicator. The following table shows the nine-level scaling method and its meaning.

1. The two elements have the same importance
2. The difference between two elements is between "equally important" and "one is slightly better than the other"
3. Compared with two elements, one is slightly better than the other
4. When comparing two elements, the difference is between "one is slightly better than the other" and "one is significantly better than the other"
5. Compared with two elements, one is obviously better than the other
6. When comparing two elements, the difference is between "one is significantly better than the other" and "one is significantly better than the other"

7. Compared with two elements, one is significantly better than the other

As shown below, taking n elements as an example, the following matrix form will be obtained.

$$(5-1)$$

Then the properties of the above matrix C are as follows:

$$(5-2)$$

In the above formula, C_{ij} represents the relative importance score between two factors.

③Consistency test:

AHP provides a set of consistency testing methods to help decision-makers determine whether the paired comparisons are self-consistent. If the consistency comparison is inappropriate, the decision maker needs to conduct a new pairwise comparison. When the judgment matrix is inconsistent, there will be corresponding eigenvalue changes, and the negative average of the eigenvalues needs to be used to make the judgment. In this case, the consistency index CI will be used, and the formula is as follows:

In the above formula, λ_{max} is the largest characteristic root of the judgment matrix. When the value is n , the CI is 0, indicating that it is completely consistent. The larger the CI value is, the greater the deviation from consistency is. In general, when $CI \leq 0.1$, the consistency is acceptable; if $CI > 0.1$, the consistency is considered unacceptable. If the value of n is larger, the consistency of the judgment will be worse, and a correction coefficient, that is, the average random consistency index RI , needs to be used, as shown in the table below.

Table 5.13 Indicator RI value

Number of indicators	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
RI value	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45

The random consistency ratio is an indicator to measure the judgment matrix. It is determined by the ratio between the consistency index CI and the average consistency index RI , as shown below:

Analysis of digital production and operation effects of Mongolian mining enterprises based on DEA

Introduction to DEA

DEA, or data envelopment analysis, is a method used to evaluate the relative efficiency of similar units. It uses linear programming technology to combine multiple input indicators and output indicators for evaluation. Under the framework of DEA, the CCR model assumes that the returns to scale of output are constant, while the BCC model allows the returns to scale to change and can subdivide the technical efficiency evaluated in the CCR model into pure technical efficiency and scale efficiency. When implementing digital transformation assessment, China State Construction adopted a strategy centered on investment indicators and used the investment-oriented BCC model for analysis. This

approach facilitates management implementation and more effectively articulates how digital transformation can increase efficiency by reducing costs and improving business performance. In the evaluation of mining enterprises, we can use mining enterprises as decision-making units and consider their resource inputs (such as capital, labor, energy, etc.) and outputs (such as mineral output, income, etc.) to evaluate their efficiency.

5.5.2 Indicator selection

Combined with the previous indicator analysis, this article determines four research indicators for analysis in five aspects. The technical dimension uses the number of R&D personnel, the information dimension uses the digital index, and the entropy method is used to determine the index. The organizational dimension uses Expenses during the operating period are used, and the cognitive dimension and management dimension use the gross profit produced at the profitability level. This article selects data related to Mongolian mining enterprises from 2014 to 2022 to provide a data basis for the research in this section and improve the reliability of the model.

First of all, the number of R&D personnel reflects the degree of human resources invested by Mongolian mining companies in digital transformation in different years. With the expansion of the R&D team, the company's innovation capabilities and application level in digital technology are expected to be improved, which is crucial to promoting the digital transformation of mining companies. Therefore, this article selects the number of R&D personnel in each year published in the annual reports of Mongolian mining companies as one of the investment indicators to evaluate the company's human resource investment in the digital transformation process.

Secondly, the amount of expenses during the operating period reflects the company's management capabilities in cost control and resource allocation. By analyzing various expenses disclosed in the annual reports of Mongolian mining companies, the total expenses during the company's operating period are calculated. This indicator is designed to measure the company's cost management efficiency in the process of digital transformation. One of the core goals of digital transformation is to reduce operating costs by optimizing processes and improving efficiency. Therefore, changes in expenses during operations can be used as an important indicator to measure the cost-effectiveness of an enterprise's digital transformation.

Thirdly, the digitalization index is calculated based on the frequency of digital transformation-related content mentioned in the annual reports of Mongolian mining companies. The more digital-related content is mentioned in the annual report, the more emphasis the company attaches to digital transformation in that year and the faster digital development. This article believes that the digitalization index is an effective indicator to measure the progress and emphasis of digital transformation of Mongolian mining enterprises. It can reflect the development level of enterprises in digitalization.

Finally, total gross profit, as a measure of a company's profitability, reflects the difference between a company's operating income and operating costs. In the study of this article, total gross profit was selected as an indicator of the output of the cognitive dimension and management dimension because cognition and management play a decisive role in the successful implementation of digital transformation. Good cognitive attitudes and effective management practices can promote the rational allocation of corporate resources and the optimization of business processes, thereby improving business profitability. The increase in total gross profit not only reflects the economic benefits of the company in digital transformation, but also shows the company's position and strength in market competition, so it has strong representativeness and reference value.

Relevant data comes from the annual reports of each company, and the data statistics are as follows.

Table 5.17 Statistics

Each parameter item	Sample	Mean	Standard deviation
Digital index	10	4.455	3.911
Number of R&D personnel	10	12897.010	5674.365
Operating expenses	10	387.041	105.812
Gross profit	10	1321.893	436.274

Outcome of Practice

In this section, using SPSSAU software, this article conducts an in-depth analysis of the annual report data of Mongolian mining enterprises from 2014 to 2022, and uses the BCC model to calculate the technical benefits, scale benefits and comprehensive benefits under the condition of variable returns to scale. As an important tool to evaluate the efficiency of decision-making units under different returns to scale conditions, the BCC model can help us more accurately understand the performance of Mongolian mining companies in the digital transformation process. By measuring the returns to scale coefficient, this study aims to reveal the specific returns to scale of Mongolian mining enterprises during their digital transformation at different stages. Through redundancy analysis, this article further explores the matching of inputs and outputs of Mongolian mining enterprises in the process of digital transformation, aiming to provide empirical basis for the digital strategy of mining enterprises, help enterprises optimize resource allocation, and improve the efficiency and efficiency of digital transformation. Effect.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

[1] Miao Laicheng, Luo Ye, DORJGOCHOO SANCHIR, et al. Main types, typical deposits, spatiotemporal distribution and structural background of copper deposits in Mongolia [J]. Acta Petrologica Sinica, 2023, 39(11): 3229 -3262.

[2] Li Weiguang, Song Houbin, Liu Haiying, et al. Orthogonal experimental study on the preparation of lightweight porous ceramics from a porphyry copper tailings in Mongolia [J]. Mineral Protection and Utilization, 2023, 43(4): 101-106.

[3] Bao Fengqin, Yongsheng, Xie Yan, et al. Analysis of geological characteristics and prospecting potential of Khanbaogedsumu mineral exploration area in South Gobi Province, Mongolia [J]. Western Resources, 2023(1):1 - 5.

[4] Li Yuxi. Analysis of the application of digital twins in the digital transformation of mining [J]. China Metal Bulletin, 2023(7):210-212.

- [5] Gao Xi, Zhang Wei, Zhao Xiangkuan, et al. Application of typical emerging frontier technologies in the mining industry under the background of digital transformation [J]. China Mining, 2022, 31(10): 23-29.
- [6] Meng Dan, Liu Jianye, Yang Bo, et al. Application of digital twins in the digital transformation of mining [J]. Nonferrous Metals (Mining Part), 2021, 73(6):9-18,31.
- [7] Build digital mines to be the leader in sustainable development - Records of the green development of Xinjiang Daming Mining Group Co., Ltd. [J]. Environmental Protection, 2023, 51(13): 68-69.
- Shvedina S A .Digital transformation of mining enterprises contributes to the rational use of resources[J].IOP Conference Series Earth and Environmental Science, 2020.
- [8] Kalenov O , Kukushkin S .Digital Transformation of Mining Enterprises[J].E3S Web of Conferences, 2021.
- Xiong L , Ning J , Wang J ,et al.Coupling degree evaluation of heavy metal ecological capacity and

